

Development of a brachytherapy surface applicator

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Purpose: For brachytherapy treatments of superficial lesions the following applicators are available: the Leipzig applicator, sets of Mould applicator, and Freiburg Flap applicator. The alternative treatment method is the implantation of needles or flexible catheters.

The development aimed to build a non-invasive surface applicator with a slow variation of depth dose curve.

Introduction: Previously, we constructed a five-channel applicator model in a pentangular source arrangement [1]. We analyzed the dose distribution with a five-channel semiconductor probe and a Mutidos and PMMA slab phantom (PTW).

Materials and methods

Recently, we redesigned the applicator, and fabricated an in-house model illustrated in Fig.1. The Iridium-192 source (Nucletron) moves in a circular catheter (A) with a 4cm diameter fixed with three dice. The 1cm thick shield (c) was moulded with Wood metal, (B) is a 5mm thick lead dice.

Fig.1. The schematic arrangement of the surface applicator

We analyzed the dose distribution with a 729 ion chamber detector array (PTW) (E), and a PMMA slab phantom (D), illustrated in Fig. 2. Dose distributions were acquired at different detector depths, with and without lead block.

Fig.2. The measurement arrangement with a 729 ion chamber array and a PMMA slab phantom

The dose distribution of a single active dwell position in a 7mm detector position is shown in Fig.3. Dose distributions at 9 to 25mm detector depth by inserting 5 mm or 1cm slabs between the applicator surface and the detector array, were acquired.

Results

Fig.3. Dose distributions of a single active dwell position beamlet measured at 7mm detector array depth, with and without the lead block

Fig.4. Radial dose profiles obtained with the Verisoft program (PTW) with and without the lead block measured at 7mm depth.

An irradiation plan was created with 26 dwell positions and 5mm steps. Dose matrices at 9 to 25 mm detector depth were acquired. Lateral dose profiles and central axis depth-dose curves were obtained with the Verisoft software, illustrated in Figs. 5 and 6.

Fig.5. Lateral dose profiles at different detector depths with and without block

Fig 6. Depth-dose curves with and without block

Conclusion

Fig7. Schematic diagram of two opposite-position beamlets

Fig.7. shows two opposite-position beamlets. At region S1, the dose distribution is built by neighboring active dwell positions beamlets, while at region S2, all active dwell positions beamlets contribute to the dose field. Since the minimal curvature radius of the Iridium-192 source is 2cm, the in-house fabricated model represents the possible smallest device. The depth-sdose curve showed lower variation until 12mm depth with block, compared to no block version. The lateral dose profiles show a 4cm diameter spot at 9mm depth, and 80% of the maximal dose.

References

1. Palvolgyi, J. Journal of Contemporary Brachytherapy (2009/volume 1/number 3)